

The Effect of Customer Orientation and Business Networking on Marketing Performance Through Competitive Advantage (Survey of Culinary Msmes In Surakarta)

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effect of entrepreneurial orientation and business networks on marketing performance through the competitive advantage of SMEs. MSMEs are required to be able to adapt the business environment and communicate innovative products in marketing to be able to reach consumers and reach target markets and reduce costs for business continuity. This research is a survey. The research population is culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. Data collection using a questionnaire. The sampling technique uses accidental sampling, as many 96 culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. Validity test uses Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and Cronbach's Alpha for reliability test. Data analysis uses Partial Least Squares (PLS). The results of the study show that entrepreneurial orientation and business networks influence marketing performance through competitive advantage. Entrepreneurial orientation and business networking have a role in improving and marketing products and expanding markets, so that MSMEs can survive and perform well during a pandemic and can increase market growth in the process of economic recovery.

KEYWORDS: entrepreneurial orientation, business network, competitive advantage, and marketing performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The President of the Republic of Indonesia has given directions to develop MSMEs to Upgrade and Modernize Cooperatives. The role of MSMEs is very large for the growth of the Indonesian economy, with the number reaching 99% of all business units. The contribution of MSMEs to GDP also reaches 60.5%, and to employment is 96.9% of the total national employment. Indonesia's economy relies heavily on MSMEs, where during the pandemic, MSMEs slumped but currently as many as 84.8% of MSMEs have returned to normal operations (<https://www.ekon.go.id>, 2022).

The growth of MSMEs has experienced an encouraging increase, indicating that MSMEs are one of the sectors of the Indonesian economy that has the ability to survive and develop into a sector that has the ability to drive the community's economy, especially small communities (Garnasih, et al, 2020). The number of MSMEs has always increased followed by an increase in the number of workers. This makes it evident that MSMEs are community economic activists. The increase in the number of MSMEs is expected to help reduce the poverty index for the people of Indonesia. Surakarta City is one of the regions in Central Java Province. Surakarta City also has various MSMEs that have become the leading potential for the region. The growth of MSMEs in Surakarta City is also moving very well, this is evident from the data from the Office of Cooperatives and SMEs (Dinkop UKM) of Surakarta City, which recorded an increase in the number of MSMEs in Surakarta City where the MSMEs assisted by the Dinkop UKM of Surakarta City in 2021 were around 3,600 MSMEs and throughout 2022 there was an increase of 50 percent, namely more than 5 thousand MSMEs were assisted by the Dinkop UKM of Surakarta City (<https://mettaneews.id/umkm-binaan-pemkotsolo-tahun-2022-meningkat-50-persen>, 2022).

MSMEs in their development also face several problems that require solutions. Garnasih, et al (2020) state that the problems faced by business actors in the MSME sector include lack of knowledge, marketing, technology, legal and financial administration, and network problems. SMEs have problems in terms of business knowledge, entrepreneurial competence, low business and labor productivity and product innovation. MSMEs are also considered to experience shortcomings in mastery of technology, management, information and markets. The problems that surround MSMEs certainly need to be minimized so that growth in the sector can be accelerated and MSME performance improved. One form of MSME business is culinary. The development of the culinary business is increasing rapidly with a variety of types in line with the demands of the increasingly complex needs of people's lives due to changes in lifestyle. In order for MSMEs in the culinary sector to win the competition, marketing their products is not only based on product quality, but also depends on the strategies that companies generally use, namely entrepreneurial orientation.

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Zeebaree and Siron (2017) state entrepreneurial orientation as an effective and efficient culture to create the behavior needed to create superior value for buyers and produce superior performance for MSMEs.

MSMEs in the culinary sector that make entrepreneurial orientation an organizational culture will be based on external basic needs, desires and market demands as a basis for formulating strategies for each business unit in the organization, and determining the competitive advantage and success of MSMEs. Culinary MSMEs that understand and have entrepreneurial abilities will have an advantage in dealing with internal and external factors of the company, so that they are better able to manage these factors into strategies that are beneficial to the company so that there are changes that provide differentiation from competitors, so that entrepreneurial orientation will have a significant effect on competitive advantage (Zeebaree and Siron, 2017) but the results of Fernanda and Sefnedi's research (2022) show different results where entrepreneurial orientation has no effect on competitive advantage.

Business implementation with a strong entrepreneurial orientation will focus on achieving superior performance by building strategies with business value creation that cannot be imitated by competitors, so that MSME actors will proactively produce innovative, creative new products or services to outperform competitors (Hernández-Perlines, 2016). MSMEs that have a high entrepreneurial orientation to take risks will gain an advantage in competing and achieve high-value performance (Medhika, et al, 2018). Wang, et al. (2020) shows the results that entrepreneurial orientation affects performance. These results differ from research from Fernanda and Sefnedi (2022) that entrepreneurial orientation has no effect on the performance of MSMEs.

One way to maintain the existence of MSMEs is to grow and strengthen their business networks. Improving the performance of MSMEs is absolutely necessary to maintain national economic stability, through the application of entrepreneurial networking (Gaol and Sigalingging, 2022). MSMEs must strengthen business networks and increase sales of MSME actors. Good MSME performance requires a business network through digital marketing as a solution to the obstacles faced by MSME actors in marketing products widely (Prabowo, 2018). MSMEs in increasing business excellence can be built with entrepreneurial networks. Garnasih, et al (2020) that business networks affect business excellence, but research by Huda, et al (2020) shows that entrepreneurial networking has a negative and insignificant effect on competitive advantage.

Yoon, et al (2018) state that business networking is a form of organization in the economic field that is used to regulate coordination and realize cooperation between elements in the organization. Gaol and Sigalingging (2022) state that business networks affect the performance of MSMEs but research by Abbas et al (2019) explains that entrepreneurial business networks have no effect on the performance of small companies.

Pradhan, et al (2018) state that competitive advantage is at the heart of marketing performance to face competition and demonstrates the ability to formulate strategies that place in a favorable position with regard to competitors. Anggraini, et al. (2022) states that by having a competitive advantage, the company will be able to survive to continue the company's life. Competitive advantage absolutely must be owned by the company / product to achieve the performance or success of the product produced. Naningsih, et al (2022) state that competitive advantage has a significant effect on the performance of MSMEs, but research by Ganarsih, et al (2020) states that competitive advantage has no effect on performance.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Each individual has a different point of view, this perspective affects the behavior of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial orientation is a creative and innovative ability that is used as a basis, and resources to seek opportunities for success. Besides business strategy, the company's entrepreneurial behavior also plays a role in achieving success (Wirawan, 2017), entrepreneurial orientation is a creative and innovative ability that is used as a basis, and a resource for finding opportunities for success (Suryana, 2014). Entrepreneurial orientation is a reflection of the inherent nature of entrepreneurs or the character and characteristics that exist in entrepreneurs and are strongwilled to realize their ideas or thoughts (Amrulloh, 2017: 48). Business networking is something that needs to be developed to make it a broad business and relationships or connections with many people to develop business (Nursholih, 2022). A business network is a form of organization in the economic field that is used to regulate coordination and realize cooperation between elements in the organization. These elements are generally in the form of business units, can also be non-business units, but are elements in a series that facilitate the implementation of business units. The organization in question can be formal or informal (Herman and Nohong, 2022). A business network is any relationship that helps in the formation of a new business as part of a network (Lestari, 2015). According to Dalimunthe (2017) competitive advantage is the ability of businesses to create competitive advantages in order to compete with competitors. According to Dewi and Seminari (2017), competitive advantage is the value of a company. from the results of implementing its strategy so that the company has more value than its competitors. David (2016) states that competitive advantage as "whatever a company does better than rival companies", when a company can do something that rival companies cannot do or has something that rival companies want, then it can represent a competitive advantage. Nursolih (2022) states that companies that can survive are companies that have strong competitiveness. Basically, every company that competes in an industrial environment has the desire to be superior to its competitors. Marketing performance is a factor that is often

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used to measure the impact of the strategy implemented by the company. The company's strategy is always directed to produce good marketing performance (such as sales volume and sales growth rate) and also good financial performance. Good marketing performance is expressed in three main quantities of value, namely sales value, sales growth, and market share (Ferdinand, 2014). Marketing performance is a measure of achievement produced by a company or organization from marketing activities as a whole. Marketing performance is also defined as a concept that measures the extent of marketing achievement by a product produced by a company (Fatmawati, 2016). Marketing performance related to customer growth is an increase in customer arrivals by repurchasing the products produced (Pardi et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

The formulation of the hypothesis in this study is:

H1 : Entrepreneurial orientation has a significant effect on the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.

Based on previous research from Halim (2018) defines entrepreneurial orientation as entrepreneurial companies related to product innovation, carrying out risky activities and the first to introduce proactive innovations and in aggressive competition, intensive activities are needed to outperform competitors which are characterized by combining aggressive postures or responses to improve positions in competition. Research conducted by Usvita (2016) states that the more entrepreneurially oriented MSMEs are, the greater the opportunity to create a competitive advantage. Fernanda and Sefnedi (2022), Gaol and Sigalingging (2022) in their research show that entrepreneurial orientation has a significant effect on competitive advantage.

H2 : Business networks have a significant effect on the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. Based on previous research from Aprizal (2018), *networking* or business networks are all relationships that help form a new business which is part of a network that involves the involvement of other business units in business activities carried out by producers, including production and product marketing activities. MSMEs need business networks to create greater efficiency in delivering goods to target markets through their connections, experience, specialization, and scale of operations and intermediaries often provide MSMEs with something more than MSMEs can achieve on their own (Nursolih, 2022). Garnasih, et al (2020) that business networks affect business excellence.

H3 : Entrepreneurial orientation has a significant effect on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. Entrepreneurial orientation as a new approach in renewing company performance by companies that are starting to try to rise from the economic downturn due to a prolonged crisis, the form of application of entrepreneurial orientation attitudes can be indicated by an indication of the ability to innovate, be proactive, and the ability to take risks. Pramesti and Giantari (2016) state that increasing entrepreneurial orientation in MSMEs will be able to improve MSME performance. Research by Hajar and Sukaatmadja (2016); Wang (2019) shows that entrepreneurial orientation has a significant effect on performance.

H4 : Business networks affect the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. Business networks involve other business units in the business activities carried out by producers, both in production and marketing of products. Manufacturers use intermediaries because they create greater efficiency in providing goods to target markets. Through contacts, experience, specialization and scale of operations, intermediaries usually offer companies more than what companies can achieve on their own (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). Gaol and Sigalingging (2022) state that business networks affect the performance of MSMEs.

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H5 : Competitive advantage has a significant effect on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs. Ekawati et al. (2016) stated that by having a competitive advantage, MSMEs will be able to survive to continue the company's life. Competitive advantage absolutely must be owned by the company/product to achieve the performance or success of the product produced. Competitive advantage is the superior position of MSMEs in the market through the distinctive competencies and strategic assets of the company. Research conducted by Hajar and Sukaatmadja (2016) found that competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on performance.

H6 : Competitive advantage mediates the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on MSME marketing performance.

Nuvriasari, et al (2017) state that, entrepreneurial orientation will increase the way of thinking and acting proactively, where the ability of SME owners will greatly affect business continuity, and owners will tend to pay attention to market changes, market needs, and the possibility of designing new products through innovation to compensate for changes in consumer wants and needs so as to improve business performance. Mahmood and Hanafi (2013) in their research found that, the partial mediating effect of competitive advantage was also found in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance. Research conducted by Alimudin (2014), Usvita (2014) and Hajar and Sukaatmadja (2016) found that competitive advantage mediates the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance.

H7 : Competitive advantage mediates the effect of business networks on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.

Herman and Nohong (2022) state that, business networks are the result of decisions and efforts by entrepreneurs to increase competitive advantage through cooperation with other business units. Higher business competitiveness can be achieved through business networks because business actors can specialize so that business is more efficient, reduce transaction costs, and increase flexibility due to trusted partners. Garnasih, et al (2020) in their research show that competitive advantage mediates the effect of business networks on marketing performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The data source in this study uses primary data. Primary data in this study came from questionnaires. The research population is the owner of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta. The sample in this study were owners of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta with the sampling technique being accidental sampling which was coincidentally encountered by researchers. The data analysis tool used to analyze the research data is the structural equation modeling (SEM) equation which has been recognized as capable of analyzing the relationship patterns owned by latent variables and indicators of these latent variables, analyzing the relationship patterns between one latent variable and another latent variable, can analyze the errors of the variables studied directly, which in essence using SEM analysis techniques produces analysis data that can answer all variable relationships presented in the study (Sujarweni, 2018). Then smartPLS (partial least square) is used as a measurement of research hypothesis testing, which is one of the methods of solving the structural equation model (SEM) tool. The selection uses partial least square (PLS) because it is one method that is more compared to other structural equation model (SEM) techniques. Partial least square (PLS) is recognized as accurately confirming the presence of theory and as explaining the presence or absence of a relationship between research latent variables. This study uses two models as data analysis testers, namely the outer model analysis test includes validity and reliability as testing each indicator. While the inner model test is used to determine the direct and indirect influence relationship of the variables studied.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Measurement Model (Outer Model) The outer model is used as a test of indicators against latent variables or in other words to measure how far the indicators relate to latent variables. Testing is done using validity and reliability measurements. Based on the model estimation results presented below, the research findings show that there are no indicators with a loading factor of less than 0.70, the criteria for individual reflexive measures are said to be high if they correlate more than 0.70 with the latent variable. construct being measured. However, factor loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 can still be maintained for the development stage model. So that the next model can be evaluated.

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Figure 2. Outer Model

The results showed that the root value of AVE (\sqrt{AVE}) of business network variables, competitive advantage, marketing performance and entrepreneurial orientation > 0.50. because the value of discriminant validity is good if the root value of AVE (\sqrt{AVE}) for each construct is higher than other constructs (variable correlation). For each indicator, the value is required to be > 0.50. Based on the data presentation, it can be stated that each variable has good discriminant validity and meets the discriminant validity criteria.

A. Uji Reliabilitas

a. Cronbach Alpha

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha Variabel

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha
Business Network	0,910
Competitive Advantage	0,789
Marketing Performance	0,853
Entrepreneurship Orientation	0,811

Source: Processed data, 2023

Based on the results of the data presentation in table 9, it is known that each research variable has a Cronbach alpha value > 0.70. Thus, the results shown from each research variable have met the reliability as a requirement for the Cronbach alpha value, so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

b. Composite Reliability

Table 4. Composite Reliability Variabel

Variabel	Composite Reliability
Business Network	0,932
Competitive Advantage	0,853
Marketing Performance	0,891
Entrepreneurship Orientation	0,865

Source: Processed data, 2023

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The results of the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha output tables show that the value of each construct is above or > 0.70, so the results can be concluded that each variable used as a research modeling estimate has good reliability or can be relied upon as a reliable measurement result because it has met the requirements.

Table 5. Measurement Outer Model

Uji Model	Output	Kriteria
Outer Model	<i>Convergent Validity</i>	A loading factor value of >0.70
	<i>Discriminat Validity</i>	The indicator value on the latent variable must be greater than the correlation of other variables by looking at the <i>cross loading</i> table.
	AVE	AVE value must be above 0.50
	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	By looking at the CR value > 0.70

Source: Processed data, 2023

B. Testing the Structural Model (Inner Model)

Table 6. Inner Model

Uji Model	Output	Kriteria
Inner Model	R2 for endogenous latent variables (<i>Q2</i>) <i>Effect Size (f2), Normed Fit Index</i>	R2 results greater than > 0.67
	Parameter coefficients and T-statistics	The estimated values for the path relationships in the structural model must be significant. Obtained by bootstrapping procedure.

Source: Processed data, 2023

The *inner model* provides an explanation of the relationship of latent variables based on research theory. This model is to determine the relationship between constructs and the predictive ability of the model. This test aims to determine how well the relationship or correlation between variables is measured using the SmartPLS analysis tool.

1. Goodness of fit a. Coefficient determination

Table 7. Coefficient Determination

Variabel	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Competitive Advantage	0.634	0.625
Marketing Performance	0.707	0.696

Source: Processed data, 2023

Based on the data presentation in the table results, it shows that the R-Square value indicates that the structural model (inner model) in this study is included in the "Strong Enough" and "Strong" model categories. The interpretation of the R-Square output in the table above can be explained as follows:

- The R-Square value of the endogenous construct of competitive advantage in the model obtained an RSquare value of 0.634. The acquisition of this value explains that the percentage of competitive advantage can be explained by entrepreneurial orientation and business networks by 63.4%, while the rest is explained by other variables outside the model variables.
- The R-Square value of the endogenous marketing performance construct in the model obtained an RSquare value of 0.707. This value explains that marketing performance can be explained by entrepreneurial orientation variables, business networks and competitive advantage by 70.7%, while the rest is explained by other variables outside the model variables.

a. Q-Square

The *goodness of fit* assessment is also known from the q-square value. The q-square value has the same meaning as the *coefficient of determination*. Where the higher the q-square, the better the model can be said to be with the data. The results of the calculation of the Q-Square value are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q\text{-square} &= 1 - [(1 - R21) \times (1 - R22)] \\
 &= 1 - [(1 - 0,634) \times (1 - 0.707)] \\
 &= 1 - (0.366 \times 0.293) \\
 &= 1 - 0,107 \\
 &= 0.893
 \end{aligned}$$

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Based on the results of the above calculations, the q-square value is 0.893. This shows that the amount of diversity of research data that can be explained by the research model is 89.3%. While the remaining 10.7% is explained by other factors that are outside this research model.

b. Effect Size (f2)

In addition to analyzing the evaluation of R2 and Q2 calculations, an evaluation analysis of the calculation of *effect size* was also carried out.

Table 8. Effect Size Value (f2)

Variabel	Business Network	Competitive Advantage	Marketing Performance	Entrepreneurship Orientation
Business Network		0,182	0,046	
Competitive Advantage			0,326	
Marketing Performance				
Entrepreneur ship Orientation		0,779	0,117	

Source: Processed data, 2023

It can be seen from the table that the data presentation on business networks to competitive advantage and marketing performance has an *effect size* value of 0.046 and 0.182, meaning that the influence given is medium on the endogenous construct. The entrepreneurial orientation variable has a medium influence on marketing performance because the *effect size* value is 0.117 and has a large influence on marketing performance because it has an *effect size* value of 0.779. The competitive advantage variable has a medium effect on marketing performance because the *effect size* value is 0.326.

c. Normed Fit Index

This measurement model, used as one of the tests in PLS with the provision that the NFI value is close to 1, the tested model has the accuracy to be used in research.

Table 9. Normed Fit Index Value

Variables	Saturated Model	Estimation Model
NFI	0,693	0,693

Source: Processed data, 2023

The results of the NFI table show that the NFI value is 0.693, which means that the contribution of the variables used is almost perfect as research, the rest of the NFI value is a factor of other variables that can be used as research.

2. Hypothesis Testing of Direct Influence

Table 10. Direct Effect of Variables

Construct	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	t-Statistic	p value
Business Network → Competitive Advantage	0,295	0,286	0,079	3,711	0,000
Business Network → Marketing Performance	0,145	0,134	0,109	1,330	0,184
Competitive Advantage → Marketing Performance	0,511	0,508	0,132	3,862	0,000
Entrepreneurial orientation → Competitive Advantage	0,611	0,623	0,084	7,227	0,000
Entrepreneurial Orientation → Marketing performance	0,283	0,295	0,143	1,981	0,048

Source: Processed data, 2023

The test results with bootstrapping in this study from PLS analysis are as follows:

➤ The effect of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage

The table results show that the original sample estimate value of organizational justice is 0.611 with a t-statistic value of 7.227 and a p value of

0.000 < 0.05. The positive original sample estimate value indicates that entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage, so that the better the entrepreneurial orientation, the more it increases the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.

➤ The effect of business networks on competitive advantage The table results show that the original sample estimate value of the business network is 0.295 with a t-statistic value of 3.711 and a p value of 0.000 < 0.05. The positive original sample estimate value

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indicates that the business network has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage, so that the better the business network, the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta will also increase.

➤ The effect of entrepreneurial orientation on marketing performance

The table results show that the original sample estimate value of entrepreneurial orientation is 0.283 with a t-statistic value of 1.981 and a p value of 0.048 <0.05. The positive original sample estimate value indicates that entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance, so that the better the entrepreneurial orientation, the more marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta will improve.

➤ The influence of business networks on marketing performance

The table results show that the original sample estimate value of the business network is 0.145 with a t-statistic value of 1.330 and a p value of 0.184 > 0.05. The positive original sample estimate value indicates that the business network has a positive but insignificant effect on marketing performance, so that the better the business network, the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta will also increase.

➤ The effect of competitive advantage on marketing performance

The table results show that the original sample estimate value of competitive advantage is 0.511 with a t-statistic value of 3.862 and a p value of 0.000 <0.05. The positive original sample estimate value indicates that competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on marketing performance, so that the better the competitive advantage, the more marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta will improve.

3. Hypothesis Testing of Indirect Effect

The results of testing the indirect effect are as follows:

Table 11. Indirect Relationship between Variables (*Indirect Effect*)

Construct	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistic	p value	Construct
Business network→ Competitive advantage→ Marketing performance	0,151	0,148	0,064	2,353	0,019	Business network Competitive advantage→ Marketing performance
Entrepreneurial orientation→ Competitive advantage→ Marketing performance	0,312	0,313	0,084	3,695	0,000	Entrepreneurial orientation→ Competitive advantage→ Marketing performance

Source: Processed data, 2023

➤ The effect of entrepreneurial orientation on marketing performance mediated by competitive advantage

To see the results of the mediation effect hypothesis test, it can be seen in the "Indirect Effects" menu. From the results of PLS analysis, it was found that competitive advantage mediates the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta with a significance of 0.000 <0.05.

➤ The effect of business networks on marketing performance mediated by competitive advantage To see the results of the mediation effect hypothesis test, it can be seen in the "Indirect Effects" menu. From the results of PLS analysis, it was found that competitive advantage mediates the effect of business networks on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta with a significance of 0.019 <0.05.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results above, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant effect on the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
2. Business networks have a positive and significant effect on the competitive advantage of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
3. Entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant effect on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
4. Business networks have no significant effect on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
5. Competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
6. Competitive advantage mediates the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.
7. Competitive advantage mediates the effect of business networks on the marketing performance of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta.

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VI. SUGGESTIONS

Suggestions that can be given include the following: Hasil

1. The results showed that business networks did not have a significant effect on marketing performance, so it can be suggested that before expanding the business network, the main thing that culinary MSMEs need to do is maintain product quality, both in terms of taste, shape, quality of ingredients used so that consumers can accept these culinary MSME products so that they can compete with other culinary and be able to improve their marketing performance.
2. Owners of culinary MSMEs in Surakarta should continue to improve entrepreneurial orientation through production innovation so as to increase competitive advantage and the impact on marketing performance is increasing.

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